

THE ROLE OF TEACHING LATIN IN THE COURSE OF SUBJECT TRAINING OF FUTURE FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHERS

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Abstract: Latin has been the only language of science, culture and writing in Western Europe for more than one and a half thousand years. The idea that the existence of scientific Latin terminology gives special importance to the study of Latin not only as the language of one of the oldest civilizations that had a great influence on the development of modern European culture, but also as the language of the etions of scientific terms is put forward in this article.

Key words: Latin language, teaching in English, medical terminology, terminoelements, aphorisms, motivation, general cultural development.

At present, there is no need to prove that the Latin language and ancient culture are the foundation of modern European civilization, the foundation and basis of humanitarian education. Latin has been the only language of science, culture and writing in Western Europe for more than a thousand and a half years. The presence of scientific Latin terminology attaches special importance to the study of Latin not only as the language of one of the oldest civilizations that had a huge impact on the development of modern European culture, but also as the language of the etymons of scientific terms. The great educational and purely practical significance of the Latin language was due to the peculiar history of its development. Latin was spoken at the beginning of the first millennium BC in the middle part of Italy, in the region of Latium, the main city of which was Rome. The political successes of the Roman state led to the subjugation of a significant part of Western Europe and Asia and Africa. Latin became the dominant spoken language throughout the newly formed Roman Empire.

One of the compulsory academic disciplines at the linguistic department is the discipline "Latin language and ancient culture", because without the achievements of ancient civilizations, the whole modern culture is unthinkable. Humanity is still turning to the legacy of previous civilizations. One of these is the civilization of Ancient Greece and Ancient Rome. With the establishment of the Roman Empire, there was a rapprochement of Roman and Greek cultures, the development of which took place on the basis of the Latin language. Latin

has long remained the language of the European world, linking the culture of modern Europe with the ancient civilizations of Greece and Rome. That is why there is a need to study Latin, in which the greatest works of world literature, scientific works on philosophy, oratory, and jurisprudence are written.

The Latin language occupies a special position among general linguistic disciplines, which is determined by the dual nature of its study: theoretical and practical. As a theoretical discipline, Latin language expands linguistic horizons and develops abstract grammatical thinking, as a practical discipline – teaches to read, analyze, translate Latin texts, assimilate Latin vocabulary, which serves as a source of international terminology with Latin phraseology. The importance of the Latin language for a person studying the history of culture and literature of Western Europe is unusually great.

Firstly, knowledge of the Latin language allows you to get acquainted in the original with numerous monuments of antiquity, the Middle Ages and later times. Informs about the Greek-Latin civilization as the basis of the culture of modern Europe. Introduces ancient mythology.

Secondly, the study of Latin is a linguistic gymnastics. It is much easier for a person who has mastered at least the basics of Latin to navigate the grammar and vocabulary of modern European languages. The fact is that the structure of many European languages is philologically close to the structure of the Latin language, and familiarity with Latin grammar makes the process of mastering other languages much easier.

Thirdly, Latin has always been the main source of the formation of the so-called international vocabulary, i.e. words common to many modern European languages and denoting important cultural phenomena. Borrowings from Latin occupy an important place in the vocabulary of various languages of Europe, including Russian, so familiarity with the vocabulary of Latin significantly helps in mastering the vocabulary of other languages. Introduces ancient mythology. Knowledge of Latin has always been considered and is considered to be the basis of European education, since the people of Europe have been creating their own culture in this language for more than 2 millennia, which is rightfully one of the most remarkable on our planet. Knowing Latin, a person gets the key to the vast layers and riches of the culture of antiquity, the Middle Ages and the Renaissance.

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